

Lamina-associated domains: tethers and looseners

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Abstract

Lamina-associated domains (LADs) are large heterochromatic regions that are positioned at the nuclear lamina (NL). A major question is how LAD–NL interactions are mediated and controlled. Here, we review recent progress in the search for molecular tethers and looseners of LADs and we discuss the link between LAD–NL tethering, transcription regulation and genome replication. We also provide a brief summary of technological advances that may uncover new aspects of LAD biology.

NL–heterochromatin interactions shape genome organization

The nuclear lamina (NL) associates with large genomic regions called Lamina Associated Domains (LADs) [1-4]. These regions comprise 30-40% of the mammalian genome. Even though LAD patterns are partially conserved between cell types and across species [5], they also exhibit cell-to-cell variation explained by cell types, cell cycle stages and the stochastic re-localisation of LADs at the NL after mitosis [6-9].

LADs are generally heterochromatic: they are enriched in the histone marks H3K9me2/3 and H3K27me3, harbor mostly inactive genes, and replicate late in S-phase [reviewed in 1]. It is still poorly understood what causes heterochromatin to be positioned at the nuclear periphery: is it largely a passive process, or is heterochromatin actively tethered to the NL by specific mechanisms? And how does this relate to the overall separation of euchromatin and heterochromatin into the so-called A and B compartments, as was discovered by Hi-C mapping [10]? One important clue comes from rare cell types, such as mouse retinal rod cells, in which heterochromatin is not at the NL but rather in the nuclear interior (sometimes referred to as "inverted" nuclei). *In silico* modelling using polymer simulations and Hi-C data from those cells indicated that attraction between heterochromatic but not between euchromatic regions is crucial for genome compartmentalization and organization. When NL-heterochromatin interactions were included in the simulations as an additional parameter, the conventional nuclear organization was re-established. This suggests that the default genome configuration is the one of the inverted nuclei, and that interactions with the NL are essential to obtain a conventional nuclear organization [11]. Several other polymer simulation studies also point towards a role of LAD-NL interactions in promoting the organization of conventional nuclei [12-15].

Mechanisms that tether LADs to the NL

Which proteins mediate these LAD-NL interactions? Lamins have been likely suspects, as they form the scaffold of the NL and can interact *in vitro* with DNA and nucleosomes [Reviewed in 16]. The combinatorial depletion of all lamins in mouse embryonic stem cells had no or only very subtle effects on the peripheral positioning of LADs [17,18]. However, recent studies showed that knock-out of Lamin B1 in human breast cancer cells or of the sole B-type lamin in *Drosophila* S2 cells led to the re-localisation of the peripheral chromatin towards the nuclear interior, chromatin decompaction and increased chromatin mobility [19,20]. Still, loss of NL interactions was generally modest and did not involve all LADs. Microscopy analysis in mouse fibroblasts has indicated that lamin C but not the closely related lamin A is important for aggregation of LADs at the nuclear periphery [21]. Expression of mutant forms of Lamin A can also cause partial re-organization of LADs [9,13,22]. Thus, it appears that lamins can contribute to LAD anchoring at the nuclear periphery in some cell types, but it is not clear yet whether this is due to a direct interaction with chromatin, or through an indirect mechanism.

Earlier studies linked the lack of both Lamin A/C and Lamin B Receptor (LBR) in mouse rod cells and olfactory neurons to their inverted nuclear organisation [23,24]. Knockout of LBR also causes partially inverted organisation in lymphocytes [11] and altered LAD–NL interactions in a leukemia cell line [25]. LBR knock-down in pre-senescent cells leads to decreased H3K9me3 levels, chromatin opening and increased expression of repeat elements that are often found in LADs [26]. Thus, LBR increasingly appears to be a key regulator of LADs in mammals.

In early embryos of *C. elegans*, the chromodomain protein Cec-4 was identified as a heterochromatin–NL tether [27]. By anchoring H3K9 methylated chromatin to the NL, Cec-4 partially modulates genome compartment A/B separation [28,29]. More strikingly, it causes stretching of

chromosomes, presumably through its NL-anchoring function [29]. Furthermore, Cec-4 dependent heterochromatin anchoring was deleterious when a pathological variant of Lamin A was expressed [30].

In mammals, several other proteins have been described as putative tethers. One interesting candidate is the widely-expressed Lamin A/C-interacting protein PRR14. This protein localises to the nuclear envelope. It contains both a lamin binding domain sufficient for its recruitment to the NL and an HP1 binding-domain [31,32]. Two other putative cell-type specific tethers that interact with Lamin B have been identified recently: Prdm16 [33] and ZKSCAN3 [34]. Understanding the driving force behind their LAD-NL tethering capacities still requires further investigation. Although all these (putative) tethers are suggested to interact with heterochromatin, but the molecular features in heterochromatin that are recognised are not clearly identified yet. However, several studies converge towards a role of H3K9me2, which is often strongly enriched at the nuclear periphery [35-37].

Clearly, LAD anchoring is mediated by multiple redundant mechanisms (Table 1, top and Figure 1, left panel) and all the (putative) tethering proteins identified so far control LAD-NL interactions only partially or in a cell-type specific manner. For most of them it is not firmly established yet whether their effects are truly direct, and what their molecular mechanisms of tethering are.

Factors that loosen NL interactions

Some euchromatic features can antagonise NL interactions. Here we refer to them collectively as *looseners*, although their mechanisms may be diverse (Table 1, bottom and Figure 1, right panel). For example, forced activation of a gene inside a LAD can lead to NL dissociation [38]. Recent DamID mapping showed that this detachment usually does not involve more than ~50 kb of DNA flanking the activated gene. Thus, the LAD does not detach in its entirety, but is instead locally remodelled. In part, this local detachment is dependent on transcription elongation [39], although transcription-independent chromatin decondensation may also play a role [38]. Conversely, inhibition of transcription can lead to increased NL interactions [39,40].

Which transcription-associated features counteract NL interactions is still poorly understood. One candidate is histone acetylation. In *C. elegans*, loss of the euchromatin binder Mrg1 compromises LAD tethering, but this appears to be an indirect effect: Mrg1 normally sequesters histone acetyl transferases in the nuclear interior, preventing histone acetylation in LADs that otherwise would trigger LAD detachment from the NL [41]. In mammalian cells, depletion of the histone deacetylase SIRT3 led to increased accessibility in LADs and weakening of LAD–NL interactions, possibly through increased histone acetylation in LADs (not measured in the study) [42]. Furthermore, in mouse cells, H3K9me2 domains were found positioned at the nuclear periphery, but not directly contacting the NL and carrying H3K27ac-marked histones [43]. It remains to be tested whether depletion of H3K27ac would allow NL contacts of these domains. Other euchromatic histone marks also appear to control NL interactions. During the *de novo* establishment of LADs in the zygote, deposition of the active histone mark H3K4me3 is required for LAD formation on the paternal chromosomes [44] but the mechanism is still unclear. It is possible to speculate that *de novo* H3K4 methylation may license regions for iLAD/LAD specification, or that heterochromatin is segregated to the NL once euchromatin has been defined. This last hypothesis, apparently in contrast with results coming from above-mentioned modelling where heterochromatin interactions seem to have a primary role in genome organization, would highlight a prominent role of euchromatin in genome organization in the zygote [11].

Interestingly, nuclear pore complexes also can counteract peripheral positioning of heterochromatin. This appears to happen during oncogene-induced senescence, which is accompanied by loss of heterochromatin from the NL, somewhat akin to the inverted organisation [45]. This re-organisation

can be attributed, at least in part, to an increased concentration of nuclear pore complexes in the nuclear envelope, which causes exclusion of heterochromatin from the NL [46]. The nucleoporin TPR is a key player in this exclusion [46,47].

Transcription repression within LADs

Classic studies have shown that artificial tethering of a genomic locus to the NL can lead to reduced gene activity, indicating that physical contact with the NL can contribute to repression [reviewed in 48]. However, one puzzle is that many LAD–NL interactions are stochastic, i.e., they occur in only a subset of cells in a population [49]. Do genes in these LADs become more active in the individual cells where they do not contact the NL? A recent study combining DamID and transcriptome analysis in single cells revealed a statistically significant correlation between NL dissociation and gene activity in LADs in individual cells [50]. These results suggest that contacts with the NL help to reinforce repression in LADs. However, the correlation was weak; it is therefore likely that LADs have a persistent heterochromatic state that maintains repression of the genes, independently of their NL association.

In developing mouse brains, LADs harbor some highly transcribed genes that show lack of H3K9me2 while retaining quite strong NL interactions, suggesting that NL binding *per se* is not repressive [8]. Likewise, deletion of *Cec-4* in *C. elegans* reduced NL contacts genome-wide but caused up-regulation of only a single gene [27]. Other recent studies also reported imperfect correlations between changes in NL interactions and changes in gene expression in response to various stimuli [18,19,51].

It is noteworthy that the nucleolus may complement the NL in gene repression, because LADs that stochastically detach from the NL are often found at the nucleolus, and such nucleolus-associated domains (NADs) generally lack transcriptional activity [reviewed in 3,52].

The degree of gene repression inside LADs is determined in part at the promoter level. By high-throughput reporter assays it was shown that some promoters are intrinsically more sensitive to this repression than others [53]. Transcription elongation also appears to be partially impeded inside LADs, suggesting that RNA polymerase pausing could contribute to transcription regulation in LADs. Similar to promoters, a subset of enhancers is also repressed by the LAD environment [53]. Paradoxically, Lamin C can bind to active enhancers in the nucleoplasm, a behavior controlled by its phosphorylation [54]. However, whether and how phosphorylated lamins control enhancer activity has not been demonstrated yet.

Taken together, these results leave little doubt that LADs are repressive chromatin domains. Evidence so far indicates that direct NL contacts are not essential for this repression, but that they may contribute in a largely redundant manner. How this works remains to be elucidated.

New roles of the NL in genome replication and mitosis

LADs are typically replicated late in S-phase [55]. Intriguingly, Rif1, a key regulator of replication timing, is enriched at the NL [56]. Upon transcriptional activation, LAD genes are not only detached from the NL but they are also replicated earlier. However, the shift in replication timing tends to involve a larger genomic region than the one detached from the NL, indicating that NL contacts and replication timing are not strictly coupled [39]. Surprisingly, in mouse myoblast cells, forced tethering of major satellite sequences (which are normally among the latest-replicated genomic loci and mostly located in the nuclear interior) to the NL caused a shift of replication timing to mid-S phase [57]. Hence, contact of LADs with the NL may help orchestrating the strict timing of replication throughout the genome. Further studies of the causal relationships between NL interactions and replication timing will require better tools to specifically disrupt these interactions.

It was generally thought that in all metazoan cells the NL dissociates at the onset of mitosis. Surprisingly, this appears not to be the case in female germline stem cells of *Drosophila*. In these cells the NL remains partially intact and surrounds the mitotic spindle, with the centrosomes embedded in this NL-like structure. Depletion of the B-type Lamin or Emerin (another NL protein) caused defects in chromosome segregation [58]. This fascinating finding extends the roles of the NL in genome maintenance.

Technologies to study LADs

In recent years several techniques have been developed enabling the mapping of NL interactions and peripheral positioning of the genome. Some of these techniques build on the original DamID technology, while others are based on new principles. In addition, technologies have been developed or refined to identify proteins that interact either with the NL or with LADs – providing entry points to identify novel tethering proteins. [Table 2](#) presents an overview of these techniques.

Outlook

Searches for LAD tethers and looseners have identified multiple candidates. However, it is a substantial challenge to conclusively determine that a particular protein is a *bona fide* LAD–NL tether. Such a protein (or protein complex) should interact with the NL (or the nuclear envelope lipid membrane), and with LADs. In addition, its depletion should lead to the detachment of LADs from the NL. This may be difficult to establish, because multiple tethers may act redundantly. Finally, for a protein to be considered a credible tether, a plausible mechanistic explanation is needed. An example of this is *C. elegans* Cec-4, which harbors a chromodomain that binds H3K9me_{2/3} as well as a domain that associates with lipid membranes [27].

For candidate looseners, several mechanisms of action can be considered. A loosener could interact directly with the genomic locus that it causes to detach from the NL. For example, it may be a component of the transcription machinery that pulls an active gene from the NL, by promoting interactions of the locus with euchromatin or with internal structures such as speckles [59] or nucleoli [reviewed in 3,52]. Alternatively, a loosener could localize at the NL and repel chromatin (e.g., the nuclear pore complex protein TPR). Again, a plausible mechanistic explanation for its action will be needed; for example: the loosener binds to a genomic locus and tethers it to a structure in the nuclear interior.

Before a protein can be considered a tether or loosener, confounding factors such as indirect effects on genome organization after loss of function of the candidate protein should be ruled out. One way to minimize such indirect effects is the use of inducible degron systems to rapidly degrade the protein of interest [reviewed in 60], combined with a method to map NL interactions genome-wide with high temporal resolution, such as pA-DamID or CUT&RUN (Table 1).

The further identification of tethers and looseners will pave the way for new functional studies, as these proteins will provide molecular handles to perturb NL interactions in a controlled manner. It will be exciting to use these handles in the future to dissect the precise causal links between LADs, the NL, and genomic functions.

Acknowledgments

We thank members of our laboratory for useful comments. We apologise to colleagues whose work we could not discuss due to the brief format of this review. Supported by ERC Advanced Grant 694466 (BvS); MSCA/AIRC iCARE2.0 fellowship 800924 (SGM), MSCA individual fellowship 838555 (SGM), MSCA individual fellowship 101023923 (LD) and La Fondation Bettencourt-Schueller. The OncoCode Institute is partly supported by KWF Dutch Cancer Society.

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Tethers

Looseners

Figure 1: Model for LAD tethers and looseners. Left panel: tethers consist of heterochromatic marks such as H3K9me2 and proteins bridging LADs with the NL. Right panel: different types of LAD looseners: active transcription, nuclear pore complexes-mediated heterochromatin repulsion, euchromatin tethering to internal structures and euchromatin-euchromatin interactions.

Table 1. Overview of putative LAD tethers and looseners across species.

Putative tethers				
Name	Description	Cell type	Species	Reference
Lamin B	- Lamina meshwork component	Embryo (S2)	Fruit Fly	[20]
Lamin B1	- Lamina meshwork component (also nucleoplasmic)	Breast cancer cells (MDA-MB-231)	Human	[19]
Lamin C	- Lamina meshwork component (also nucleoplasmic)	Embryonic fibroblasts	Mouse	[21]
Lamin A	- Lamina meshwork component (also nucleoplasmic)	Cardiomyocytes	Human	[9]
		Fibroblasts (HDF)	Human	[22]
LBR	- Nuclear envelope protein - Binds Lamin B - Interacts with HP1	Rod cells	Mouse	[23]
		Olfactory neurons	Mouse	[24]
		Lymphocytes	Mouse	[11]
		Leukemia (K562)	Human	[25]
		Fibroblasts (WI-38)	Human	[26]
Cec-4	- Nuclear envelope protein - Binds H3K9me2/3	Early embryo	Worm	[27, 28, 29]
PRR14	- Nuclear periphery protein - Binds HP1 - Contains a lamina binding domain (LBD)	HeLa	Human	[31, 32]
Prdm16	- Interacts with Lamin B - Mediates heterochromatin tethering at the nuclear periphery	Fibro-adipogenic progenitors	Mouse	[33]
ZKSCAN3	- Interacts with nuclear lamina components. - Stabilizes heterochromatin	Mesenchymal stem cells	Human	[34]

Putative looseners				
Name	Description	Cell type	Species	Reference
Chromatin de-condensation	- Mechanism unknown - Sufficient to promote detachment from NL	Embryonic stem cells	Mouse	[38]
Active transcription	- Mechanism unknown - Possible dependence on chromatin de-condensation	Embryonic stem cells	Mouse	[39]
Histone acetylation	- Mechanism unknown - Could promote de-condensation	Intestinal cells	Worm	[41]
		Mesenchymal stem cells	Human	[42]
TPR	- Nucleopore component	Fibroblasts (IMR-90)	Human	[46]
		HeLa	Human	[47]

Table 2. Overview of the recent techniques to study LADs.

Technology	Description	Output	Reference
pA-DamID	Antibody-mediated recruitment of Dam to NL components coupled to NGS.	Provides increased temporal resolution compared to <i>in vivo</i> DamID. Can be coupled to visualization of LADs with ^{m6} A-tracer before sequencing. Provides control for accessibility by using freely diffusible Dam.	[7]
TSA-seq	Antibody-directed deposition of biotin-tyramide to mark DNA that is in proximity of the NL or other nuclear structures.	Generates genome-wide maps of cytological distances from the NL and other nuclear compartments.	[59]
scDam&T	Simultaneous Lamin B1 DamID and RNA-seq in single cells.	Allows quantification of NL contact frequency and gene expression in the same cell.	[50]
μDamID	DamID coupled to microfluidics.	Allows the visualization of LADs in a single cell before processing for scDamID.	[61]
Nanopore DamID	DamID coupled to single molecule Nanopore sequencing.	Detection of ^{m6} A and ^{m5} C in the same DNA molecules, allowing the measurement of LAD methylation status.	[62]
Lamin B1 CUT&RUN	Antibody-mediated recruitment of MNase to Lamin B1, coupled to NGS.	Provides high resolution of LAD patterns with low input material. Requires proper control for accessibility.	[8]
APEX-seq	Fusion of the APEX enzyme to Lamin B1.	Enables biotinylation of RNA, DNA and proteins in proximity of the NL.	[63]
^{m6} ATurbo-ID	Fusion of BirA to m6A-tracer.	Maps the LAD proteome.	[64]
Multiplexed FISH	Sequential hybridization of probes along a desired location.	Allows the 3D reconstruction of a given locus in single cells, and locus positional information relative to nuclear compartments.	[40]
Chromosome paint	Chromosome paint using sets of probes differentiating LADs from iLADs on the same chromosome.	Allows visualization of LADs versus iLADs on a single chromosome. Chromatin compaction state can also be inferred.	[21]